

THE RELATIONSHIP OF ONLINE LEARNING WITH THE ANXIETY LEVEL OF NEW STUDENTS OF APPLIED NURSING ANESTHESIOLOGY (STKA) STUDENTS OF THE YOGYAKARTA KEMENKES HEALTH POLYTECHNIC

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Abstract

Background: Online learning is considered to be the best solution for teaching and learning activities in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic. Although agreed upon, this study caused controversy. For teachers, online learning is only effective for assignments, while making students understand online learning materials is considered difficult. In addition, the technological and economic abilities of each student are different. Not all students have facilities that support online learning activities. Students often experience anxiety disorders, one of which is the result of psychosocial factors, where students do not respond appropriately and accurately to stressors, for example to new environmental situations. If anxiety cannot be overcome, it can interfere with student achievement results during online learning, besides causing students to be less focused on receiving the material presented by the lecturer. Research purposes: To find out the Relationship between Online Learning and Anxiety Levels of New Students Sarjana Terapan Keperawatan Anestesiologi (STKA) Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta. Method: Bivariate analysis was used to describe the relationship between independent variables, confounding variables and dependent variables using Spearman's test. Results: Online learning in most categories is sufficient. The anxiety level of new students is in the medium category. There is a relationship between online learning and the anxiety level of new students with a p value of 0.00. Conclusion: There is a relationship between online learning and the anxiety level of new students in Sarjana Terapan Keperawatan Anestesiologi (STKA) Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta.

Keywords: Online Learning, Anxiety Level of New Students STKA.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) designated the 2019 Corona virus disease or Covid-19 as a global pandemic in terms of its very fast and comprehensive spread throughout the world (WHO, 2020). Covid-19 is a new type of disease and is very easily transmitted. This new virus was previously unknown before infecting many residents of Wuhan, China and causing an outbreak there in December 2019 (Ministry of Health, 2020). Efforts are always made to prevent and slow the spread of the virus, one of which is social distancing and physical distancing. The change from social distancing to physical distancing by WHO aims to break the chain of spread of the virus. Physical distancing aims to protect everyone's physical condition, so this effort is starting to be implemented in all sectors, including the education sector (WHO, 2020). Implementation in the education sector has an impact on changes in learning methods (WHO, 2020). Tribun Jogja News on August 10 2020, the Governor of the Special Region of Yogyakarta, Sri Sultan Hamengku Buwono X, also decided not to allow face-to-face or direct learning. Direct face-to-face learning will be implemented in stages, starting from the highest level, namely lectures. Deputy Chair of the Yogyakarta Special Region DPRD, Huda Tri Yudianta, said that the presence of students returning to face-to-face learning on their respective campuses should also

not be carried out simultaneously and completely. As a result of the global Covid-19 pandemic, all campuses have been encouraged to conduct online lectures in order to break the chain of spread of Covid-19 (Tabroni, 2020).

Online learning is considered to be the best solution for teaching and learning activities in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic. Even though it was agreed, this study caused controversy. For teaching staff, online learning is only effective for assignments, while making students understand online learning material is considered difficult. In addition, the technological and economic capabilities of each student are different. Not all students have facilities that support online learning activities. Inadequate internet connections, unsupported devices, and expensive internet quotas are obstacles to online learning. However, learning must continue. Each education provider has its own policy in responding to this rule. Several higher education institutions provide internet quota subsidies to students to carry out online learning (Maulana & Hamidi, 2020).

Students are one group of people who are vulnerable to mental health problems (Qaisy, 2011). Several studies have demonstrated high levels of psychological morbidity in college students worldwide, particularly related to depression and anxiety. This is supported by findings showing that among all students who seek counseling services, the main problem most often brought up is anxiety, followed by problems related to academics and work (Safree, Yasin & Dzulkifli, 2011). Students often experience anxiety disorders, one of which is the result of psychosocial factors, where students do not respond appropriately and accurately to stressors, for example new environmental situations. Anxiety disorders can affect the teaching and learning process in students because with this disorder a person will experience distortions in information processing. This can interfere with the ability to concentrate, reduce memory, and so on. So it can disrupt the learning process for students (Chandratika & Purnawati, 2014).

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Based on research by Kurniawan and Ngapiyem (2020), emotional mental disorders in first semester students can occur as a result of the transition process from High School (SMA) to University (PT) which requires adjustment. This problem can be described by screening using the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale 42 (DASS 42) instrument with the results of 94 respondents (67%) experiencing anxiety, 25 respondents (18%) divided into mild anxiety categories, 48 respondents (34%) with moderate anxiety.), severe anxiety 16 respondents (11%), and very severe anxiety 5 respondents (4%) (Kurniawan & Ngapiyem, 2020). Female gender, student status,

certain physical symptoms and self-rated health status were significantly associated with greater psychological impact of the outbreak and higher levels of stress, anxiety and depression (Rajkumar, 2020). Setiyani's (2018) research shows that new students at the Faculty of Health Sciences (FIKES) are more anxious and more depressed than non-FIKES/FEISHum students (Faculty of Economics, Social Sciences & Humanities). Researchers concluded that there were differences in anxiety and depression between new students at FIKES and Non-FIKES, where new FIKES students were more anxious and depressive than new students at Non-FIKES/FEISHum. FIKES students are students from the Faculty of Health Sciences, where the practicum and lecture schedule is very busy. Meanwhile, Non-FIKES are students from the Faculty of Economics, Social Sciences and Humanities (FEISHum). Heavy duties and responsibilities can be a stressor that causes anxiety and depression. Data analysis used the T test with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

In research by Kusnayat, et al (2020) it shows that around 60.5% of students are ready to adapt to the use of online lecture learning technology but around 59.5% object to the assignments given by lecturers which results in student stress levels of around 60%. If this is allowed to continue, it will have fatal consequences for students' psychological development, and as many as 92% of students choose and prefer face-to-face lectures in class compared to online lectures. So this research shows a close relationship between online lectures and students' mental attitudes.

Yogyakarta Ministry of Health Health Polytechnic or Poltekkes Yogyakarta is a tertiary institution located in Sleman, Yogyakarta which provides education for health workers at Diploma III and Diploma IV levels, under the auspices of the Center for Health Worker Education, Health Human Resources Development and Empowerment Agency, Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia. It has 6 majors, one of which is nursing. The nursing department itself is divided into several study programs, one of which is the Bachelor of Applied Nursing which takes 8 semesters. In lectures you not only learn nursing theory, but there is also practice of nursing skills starting from level 1 of lectures. The condition of the Covid-19 pandemic means that new students majoring in nursing in the undergraduate applied nursing study program do not yet understand the learning system on campus due to the transition from high school with face-to-face learning to lectures that begin online. Meanwhile, campus introductions or often called PKKMB are carried out online so that students only know what the resource person said during the PKKMB.

Based on a preliminary study conducted on 10 new students of the Applied Anesthesiology Nursing Undergraduate Study Program (STKA) Nursing Department, Health Polytechnic, Ministry of Health, Yogyakarta, from the results of questions and answers via chat via WhatsApp, 9 students said they were worried because their first lecture used an online system, whereas previously high school did nothing at all. not yet familiar with online learning. Apart from that, the internet network is unstable, the learning environment is less conducive and the workload often increases with short assignment submission times, these are factors that can cause anxiety. If anxiety cannot be overcome, it can disrupt student achievement results during online learning, besides causing students to be less focused on receiving the material presented by the lecturer. Based on these problems, researchers conducted research with the title "The Relationship between Online Learning and the Anxiety Level of New Students of the Bachelor of Applied Anesthesiology Nursing (STKA) Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta".

RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research is non-experimental quantitative descriptive research, namely research to create an objective picture of a situation which is carried out without intervening with the research subject. This research method is a correlation study, which is essentially research about the relationship between two or more variables in a situation or group of subjects (Notoatmodjo, 2018).

This research design uses cross sectional, a study to study correlation dynamics using a participatory observation approach or collecting data at one time. This means that each research subject is only observed once and measurements are made of the subject's character status or variables at the time of the examination, but this does not mean that all research subjects are observed at the same time (Notoatmodjo, 2018).

The population is the entire research object that concerns the problem being studied. These variables can be people, events, behavior or something that will be researched (Notoatmodjo, 2018). The population in this study were new students from the Bachelor of Applied Anesthesiology Nursing Study Program (STKA) Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta, totaling 35 students.

In this study, researchers used a sampling technique, namely total sampling. The sampling method is a sampling technique where the number of samples is the same as the population (Sugiyono, 2017). So in this study, after the sample meets the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the entire sample will be taken. In general, for correlational research, the minimum number of samples required for good results is 30 and a maximum of 500 samples (Sugiyono, 2017).

Researchers in this study took respondents as samples with several criteria as follows:

1. Inclusion criteria:

- a. Level 1 student of the Nursing Department, Applied Anesthesiology Nursing Undergraduate Study Program (STKA) Health Polytechnic, Ministry of Health, Yogyakarta.
- b. Participate in online learning or virtual learning from July 2021 to December 2021
- c. In 1 semester there is a laboratory practice schedule
- d. Fill out informed consent
- e. Fill out the questionnaire in full

2. Exclusion criteria:

- a) Level 2, 3 and 4 students of the Nursing Department, Applied Nursing Anesthesiology Undergraduate Study Program (STKA) Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta
- b) Not filling out informed consent
- c) Students who do not fill out the questionnaire completely.

The research location is at the Yogyakarta Ministry of Health Polytechnic Campus

This research was conducted from July 2021 to October 2021.

A variable is anything in any form that is determined by the researcher to be studied so that information about it is obtained, then conclusions are drawn. A variable can be defined as something that is used as a characteristic, trait or measure that is owned or obtained by a research unit regarding a particular concept (Notoatmodjo, 2018).

1. Independent Variable (independent)

The independent variable is the variable that is the cause of the change or emergence of the dependent variable. An independent variable means being free to influence other variables (Hidayat, 2017). The independent variable in this research is online learning

2. Dependent Variable

The dependent variable is a variable that is influenced or a result of the independent variable (Hidayat, 2017). The dependent variable in this research is the anxiety level of new students

Data analysis used the Spearman test

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Characteristics of respondents based on gender, age and place of residence of new students majoring in Nursing, Applied Nursing Anesthesiology Undergraduate Study Program (STKA) Yogyakarta Ministry of Health Health Polytechnic

No	Respondent Characteristics	Category	Amount	
			f	%
1.	Gender	Man	6	17,14
		Woman	29	82,86
2.	Age (Years)	17	8	22,86
		18	8	22,86
		19	9	25,71
		20	10	28,57
3.	Residence	House	23	65,71
		Kos	12	34,29

Based on table 1, it can be seen that the majority of gender is female as many as 29 students (82.86%). The majority were 20 years old, 10 respondents (28.57%). The majority of students' residence when online learning took place was at home, 23 students (65.71%).

Table 2: Online learning system for new students of the Nursing Department, Applied Nursing Anesthesiology Undergraduate Study Program (STKA) Health Polytechnic, Ministry of Health, Yogyakarta

Online learning system	Amount	%
Not Enough	8	22,86
Enough	13	37,14
Good	8	22,86
Very Good	6	17,14
Total	35	100

Based on table 2 above, it can be seen that the online learning system for new students of the Nursing Department of the Undergraduate Study Program in Applied Nursing Anesthesiology (STKA) of the Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health of Yogyakarta is mostly sufficient with 13 respondents (37.14%).

Table 3: Anxiety levels of new students majoring in the Nursing Program Applied Undergraduate Studies in Anesthesiology (STKA) Yogyakarta Ministry of Health Health Polytechnic

Anxiety level	f	%
Normal	8	22,86
Ligth	9	25,71
Currently	12	34,29
Heavy	4	11,43
Very Heavy	2	5,71
Total	35	100

Based on table 3 above, it can be seen that the anxiety level of new students of the Bachelor of Applied Nursing Anesthesiology (STKA) Nursing Department, Health Polytechnic, Ministry of Health, Yogyakarta, is mostly in the moderate anxiety level category, with 12 respondents (34.29%).

The relationship between the online learning system and the anxiety level of new students in the Bachelor of Applied Nursing Anesthesiology Study Program, Nursing Department, Health Polytechnic, Ministry of Health, Yogyakarta

The relationship between the online learning system and anxiety levels was analyzed using the Spearman test. The independent variable is said to have a significant relationship with the anxiety level of new students of the Bachelor of Applied Nursing Anesthesiology Study Program, Nursing Department, Health Polytechnic, Ministry of Health, Yogyakarta if the p-value is <0.05.

Based on testing for the relationship between the online learning system and the anxiety level of new students in the Bachelor of Applied Nursing Anesthesiology Study Program, Nursing Department, Health Polytechnic, Ministry of Health, Yogyakarta, it shows a correlation coefficient value of -0.741 with a significance (p) value of 0.000 (p<0.05), so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between the online learning system and the anxiety level of new students. The direction of the correlation is negative, meaning that the better the online learning system, the lighter it will be or even the student's anxiety level will be relatively normal. Vice versa, the less good the online learning system, the greater the level of anxiety for new students of the Bachelor of Applied Anesthesiology Nursing Study Program, Nursing Department, Health Polytechnic, Ministry of Health, Yogyakarta.

Based on general data on housing, students who live in boarding houses experience a lot of anxiety, because the situation in the boarding house is different from the situation at home because they have to live separately from their parents, they have to face various problems on their own without the help of their parents. The similarity between student anxiety is that with online learning students must need sufficient funds so that online learning can run well. This is the same as the results of Dewi's (2020) research regarding the residence of respondents who were separated from their parents, many of whom experienced moderate anxiety. Online learning is learning without direct face-to-face interaction between lecturers and students, but carried out online.

Online learning is carried out via video conference, e-learning or distance learning. Online learning is something new, both for students and lecturers, so it takes quite a long time to adapt (Hakiman, 2020). The positive and negative impacts of online

learning are that students can get material easily and learn to evaluate their own learning wherever they are, both at home and in other public places, while the negative impact is that many students abuse the online learning system and use their study time for other things. Which could be considered less important, and that could be detrimental to himself (Eko Putra 2020). The impact of this learning system is student anxiety and this can cause a decrease in achievement. Online learning students feel anxious because they have to adapt online lectures to applications that have previously been used.

They feel anxious because with online lectures there are more assignments compared to teaching courses, and also with online learning whether they can get a good GPA. Many factors influence learning achievement, including the goals to be achieved, influencing situations, students' readiness to study, students' interest and concentration in studying, time and readiness to study, because there are many factors that influence the educational process. Psychological factors also influence a person's learning motivation and learning achievement. Some of the main factors are student intelligence, interests, attitudes, talents and self-confidence.

The learning environment according to Saroni (2006) is that everything related to the place where the learning process is carried out, including the facilities, seems to have been a commitment of the founders from the start. This can be seen, for example, from the availability of very adequate e-learning learning facilities. In theory, according to (Nevid, 2010) anxiety is a state of apprehension or a state of worry that complains that something bad will happen soon. Anxiety becomes abnormal if the level is out of proportion, threatening or if it seems to come without any cause, that is, if it is not a response to changes in the environment. Excessive anxiety can cause students to experience psychosomatic problems. Psychosomatic symptoms that can be experienced are feelings of anxiety, tension, fear, apprehension, sleep disorders, intelligence disorders, feelings of depression (gloomy), somatic/physical (muscle) symptoms, somatic/physical (sensory) symptoms, cardiovascular symptoms, respiratory symptoms, gastrointestinal (digestion), urogenital symptoms, autonomic symptoms, and behavioral symptoms (attitude) (Hamilton in Mcdowell, 2006). When experiencing anxiety, the body's system will increase the work of the sympathetic nervous system, causing changes in the body's response (Patimah, Suryani, & Nuraeni, 2015).

Based on general data on where respondents live, there is no relationship between anxiety, but it appears that students who live in dormitories and boarding houses experience the most moderate anxiety. They have to live separately from their parents, they have to face various problems on their own without their parents' help. The similarity between student anxiety is that with online learning students must need sufficient credit funds so that online learning can run well.

CONCLUSION

Online learning in most categories is sufficient. The anxiety level of new students of the Bachelor of Applied Anesthesiology Nursing Study Program (STKA) is in the moderate anxiety category. There is a relationship between online learning and the anxiety level of new students of the Bachelor of Applied Anesthesiology Nursing (STKA) Nursing Department, Health Polytechnic, Ministry of Health, Yogyakarta.

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